

Involvement of liver kinase B1 in the ameliorative action of epigallocatechin-3-gallate against MAFLD progression in mice

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Received 16 May 2025 ♦ Accepted 14 July 2025 ♦ Published 13 August 2025

Citation: Rahmadi M, Phan C-W, Balan SS, Zumarthana AS, Ayundari EM, Putri IWYP, Salsabila, Nurhan AD (2025) Involvement of liver kinase B1 in the ameliorative action of epigallocatechin-3-gallate against MAFLD progression in mice. *Pharmacia* 72: 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.3897/pharmacia.72.e159024>

Abstract

Metabolic dysfunction-associated fatty liver disease (MAFLD) is characterized by intrahepatic fat accumulation in individuals without a history of excessive alcohol consumption. This study investigated the effects of epigallocatechin-3-gallate (EGCG) on reducing MAFLD severity. Twenty-four ddY mice were divided into three groups: normal feed, high-fat diet (HFD), and HFD + 25 mg/kg EGCG supplementation. All mice were provided with food and water *ad libitum*; the remaining feed and body weight were measured daily for 28 days. On the 15th day, the therapy group received EGCG intraperitoneally. At the end of the study, mice were sacrificed, and their livers were collected for histopathological examination and measurement of LKB1, CD86, and CD163 mRNA expression. The results indicated that LKB1 expression increased significantly following EGCG administration. Additionally, histopathological analysis revealed a positive impact of EGCG on hepatocyte repair. In conclusion, the 14-day EGCG treatment demonstrated promising results in improving liver health in mice with MAFLD and modulating LKB1 expression.

Keywords

metabolic dysfunction-associated fatty liver disease, steatosis, EGCG, high-fat diet, liver kinase B1

Introduction

Hepatic steatosis, commonly referred to as fatty liver or fatty liver disease, is characterized by intrahepatic fat accumulation of at least 5% of the liver's weight. The liver's initial build-up of triglycerides (TG) is a hepatoprotective mechanism.

However, if this accumulation of liver fat persists, it leads to hepatic metabolic dysfunction, inflammation, and the potential development of complex fatty liver diseases (Nassir et al. 2015). Metabolic dysfunction-associated fatty liver disease (MAFLD) is the leading global cause of chronic liver disease. It is defined as the presence of macrovesicular

steatosis in $\geq 5\%$ of hepatocytes in individuals who consume little to no alcohol (Loomba et al. 2013; Nassir et al. 2015).

The term MAFLD encompasses a spectrum of disease stages, ranging from simple fat accumulation (steatosis, also referred to as non-alcoholic fatty liver or NAFL) to steatohepatitis (MASH), followed by the development of fibrosis, and potentially progressing to cirrhosis and hepatocellular carcinoma (HCC) (Ratziu et al. 2010; Ruissen et al. 2020). While only a small percentage of patients with hepatic steatosis develop advanced-stage liver disease, the progression of MAFLD to more severe liver conditions can lead to potentially life-threatening complications (Ruissen et al. 2020). Unfortunately, identifying patients at high risk for MAFLD progression is challenging due to the absence of reliable clinical biomarkers for early-stage MAFLD (Huang et al. 2022). Consequently, this study aims to investigate promising functional compounds that may ameliorate or slow disease progression, particularly in the early stages of MAFLD.

The pathogenesis of MAFLD is commonly called the “two-hit theory.” In the first hit, insulin resistance leads to increased food intake and enhanced liver fat production, accumulating TG and free fatty acids (FFA) in the liver. In the second hit, excess FFA exacerbates fatty acid oxidation within the liver, leading to the overproduction of superoxide, which damages hepatocyte mitochondria and impairs the synthesis of sufficient adenosine triphosphate (ATP) necessary for normal hepatocyte function. This disruption causes alterations in lipid and glucose metabolism and disturbances in protein synthesis (Zeng and Chen 2022). Moreover, the second hit triggers an inflammatory and fibrogenic cascade, causing inflammation and fibrosis (Leamy et al. 2013).

Adiponectin is an adipokine whose expression and circulating levels are diminished in individuals with obesity, and it exerts anti-diabetic effects (Fisher et al. 2005). This protein plays a crucial role in regulating immune responses, particularly inflammation, and is a significant mediator in the pathogenesis of obesity-induced insulin resistance (Esmaili et al. 2014). Adiponectin interacts with two types of receptors, namely AdipoR1 and AdipoR2 (Kadowaki et al. 2006; Luo and Liu 2016). AdipoR1 mediates the inhibitory effects of adiponectin on NF- κ B activation and the subsequent transcription of pro-inflammatory cytokines such as TNF- α , IL-6, and IL-8 in macrophages (Luo and Liu 2016). In addition, adiponectin engages AdipoR2 to promote M2 polarization in macrophages (Mandal et al. 2011). Macrophages are immune cells that play vital roles in various physiological and pathological processes, including organ development, host defense, acute and chronic inflammation, and tissue homeostasis and remodeling. Macrophage polarization can be classified into two types: classically activated macrophages (M1), which drive pro-inflammatory responses, and alternatively activated macrophages (M2), which are involved in immune regulation and tissue remodeling (Wang et al. 2019).

Epigallocatechin-3-gallate (EGCG) is the most abundant antioxidant catechin found in green tea (*Camellia sinensis*). It exhibits a range of pharmacological activities, including anticancer, anti-inflammatory, and anti-allergic

effects, particularly through its interaction with the 67-kDa laminin receptor (67LR) (Fujimura et al. 2022). Research has indicated that EGCG consumption can have beneficial effects on MAFLD, particularly in regulating metabolism, enhancing antioxidant activity, modulating the anti-inflammatory response, and providing antifibrotic effects (Tang et al. 2021). Additionally, EGCG has been shown to inhibit the activation of extracellular signal-regulated kinase (ERK1/2), increase the expression of peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor gamma (PPAR γ), and decrease PPAR γ phosphorylation (Santamarina et al. 2015). PPAR γ is a transcription factor that plays a crucial role in regulating lipid metabolism, maintaining energy homeostasis, and promoting adiponectin gene expression in adipose tissue.

While some studies have demonstrated the protective effects of EGCG against steatosis and oxidative stress induced by fatty liver, research regarding EGCG's role in fibrosis within MAFLD and its mechanisms involving AMPK activation through LKB1 and adiponectin remains limited. Therefore, this study aims to investigate the protective mechanisms of EGCG in the progression of MAFLD and inflammation in a mouse model of MAFLD induced by HFD, focusing on the SIRT1-LKB1-AMPK pathway and the polarization of M1 and M2 macrophages.

Materials and methods

Experimental animals

Twenty-four male ddY mice, aged 2 to 3 months and weighing approximately 25 to 35 grams, were utilized in this study. The mice were housed in plastic cages with bedding made of wood chips, maintained at room temperature (22 ± 2 °C), and subjected to a 12-hour light and 12-hour dark cycle. All experimental animals were acclimatized to the rearing environment for seven days prior to treatment. This research was conducted at the Animal Laboratory Research Center within the Faculty of Pharmacy, Universitas Airlangga. All protocols for this study were approved by the research ethics committee of the Faculty of Veterinary Medicine at Universitas Airlangga (Animal Care and Use Committee), under research ethics certificate No. 2.KEH.097.06.2023.

Drugs and experimental design

EGCG isolate was obtained from Professor Djoko Agus Purwanto (Universitas Airlangga, Indonesia). EGCG suspension was freshly prepared daily prior to administration by dissolving it in 5% Tween 80 (NaCl 0.9%). In this study, 24 mice were randomly divided into three groups ($n = 8$): (1) mice fed a normal chow diet for 28 days; (2) mice fed HFD for 28 days and injected intraperitoneally (i.p.) with 5% Tween 80 from the 15th day to the 28th; and (3) mice fed HFD for 28 days and injected i.p. with EGCG at a dosage of 25 mg/kg from the 15th day to the 28th, serving as the therapy group. The HFD used in this

study consisted of 60% beef tallow, which was melted on a hotplate at 60 °C and subsequently blended with 15% cornstarch. This mixture was then combined with 25% of the normal feed after being thoroughly mashed to achieve a homogeneous consistency (Rahmadi et al. 2021). Mice were fed pellets weighing 8 to 12 g according to their treatment groups. The remaining pellets and the body weight of the mice were weighed daily to evaluate food intake and body weight, respectively. The experimental design is schematically illustrated in Fig. 1.

Histopathological examination

After 28 days of treatment, all mice in each group were sacrificed, and their livers were extracted. Tissue samples were removed immediately post-mortem, fixed in 10% formalin, processed, and embedded in paraffin. Subsequently, 3 µm sections were sliced and stained with hematoxylin and eosin (HE). The resulting slides were examined under an optical microscope, and digital images were captured. Histological features of the liver, including steatosis, inflammation, and ballooning, were analyzed using a scoring system based on the NAFLD activity score (NAS).

Assessment of LKB1, CD86, and CD163 mRNA expression

The liver tissue samples collected for molecular analysis were subsequently stored in a freezer at -80 °C. The mRNA expression levels of LKB1, CD86, and CD163 in the liver were quantified using reverse transcription quantitative polymerase chain reaction (RT-qPCR). All tissue samples were purified for total RNA using the PureLink™ RNA Mini Kit (Life Technologies, USA), followed by reverse transcription with the GoScript™ Reverse Transcription System (Promega, USA), and PCR amplification using GoTaq® DNA Polymerase (Promega, USA). The primers utilized in this study were as follows: LKB1 (fwd: 5'-TTGGCCTTTTCTC-CGAGG-3'; rev: 5'-CAGGTCCCCCATCAGGTACT-3'), CD86 (fwd: 5'-GTACCTGCTAAGGATCCGAC-3'; rev: 5'-CCTAAGCGATCCGTTGCAG-3'), and CD163

(fwd: 5'-ACTTCAGAATCACATCATGGCACA-3'; rev: 5'-ACTTCAGAATCACATCATGGCACA-3'). The relative expression levels of the target mRNA were determined using the comparative cycle threshold (Ct) method, which involved normalizing the Ct values of the target mRNA to those of β-actin.

Data analysis

Percentage changes in body weight and food intake profile data were statistically analyzed using a two-way analysis of variance (ANOVA), followed by post hoc analysis with the Sidak test. The histopathological parameters were also evaluated using the two-way ANOVA method, followed by Tukey's post hoc test. The relative expressions of LKB1, CD86, and CD163 mRNA were assessed using a one-way ANOVA, followed by Tukey's post hoc test. Data were analyzed using GraphPad Prism 9.0.2 software (GraphPad, Inc., USA). All profile data are presented as mean ± SEM.

Results

The effect of EGCG on the body weight profile of mice

The results indicated that the group of mice fed a normal diet experienced an increase in body weight of approximately 8.10% after 28 days of treatment. In contrast, the group of mice that received HFD exhibited a weight loss of about 34.33% from baseline. Furthermore, the group of mice given HFD along with EGCG at a dosage of 25 mg/kg intraperitoneally for 14 days demonstrated a weight reduction of 38.18% (Fig. 2).

The effect of EGCG on the food intake profile of mice

The food intake profile for each mouse was determined by weighing the remaining feed daily over a period of 28 days. In the group of mice fed a normal chow diet, the

Figure 1. Experimental design scheme.

Figure 2. Body weight profile of each group. $**p \leq 0.01$ significant against normal chow group. Data are shown as mean \pm SEM (n = 8).

average food intake was approximately 4 to 5.5 g per day, providing 306.2 kcal per 100 g. In contrast, the HFD and therapy groups consumed about 1 to 3 g per day, with a caloric content of 671.75 kcal per 100 g. The results indicated that while the food intake of the groups receiving the HFD was significantly reduced (Fig. 3A), the caloric intake remained similar across all groups (Fig. 3B).

The effect of EGCG on liver histopathology of mice

Histological examination of the liver was conducted using an optical microscope at 200x magnification. Microscopic observations revealed that the liver histopathology of mice fed a chow diet exhibited nuclei within cells, accompanied by cytoplasm and sinusoids arranged in a consistent pattern around the central vein (Fig. 4A). In the normal chow group, the total NAS was 0 (Fig. 5). In contrast, the group fed HFD displayed notable abnormalities in hepatocyte cell structure, characterized by the presence of inflammatory cells, ballooning degeneration, and lipid droplets (steatosis), specifically macrovesicular steatosis (Fig. 4B). This group had an average total NAS of 4.6, indicating that it had progressed to the MAFLD stage and crossed

the threshold of MASH (Fig. 5). Furthermore, in the group that received EGCG at a dosage of 25 mg/kg, improvements were observed in the livers of the mice. The structure of several cells appeared relatively normal, although some cells still exhibited ballooning degeneration and the presence of steatosis. In this group, inflammatory cells were no longer observable (Fig. 4C). The average total NAS in this group was 2.4, indicating that it had entered the MAFLD stage but had not yet reached the MASH category (Fig. 5).

The effect of EGCG on LKB1 mRNA expression

In the group that received HFD for 28 days, there was a significant decrease in the expression of LKB1 mRNA in the liver. Subsequently, the administration of EGCG at a dose of 25 mg/kg from the 15th day to the 28th resulted in a significant increase in the relative mRNA expression of LKB1 compared to the HFD group (Fig. 6).

The effect of EGCG on macrophage polarization

Fig. 7A illustrates that the relative expression of CD86 (M1) mRNA in the HFD group was higher than that in the control group and the HFD + EGCG 25 mg/kg group, although this difference was not statistically significant. Conversely, Fig. 7B indicates that the relative expression of CD163 (M2) mRNA in the HFD + 25 mg/kg group tended to be higher compared to both the normal chow group and the HFD group, but again, this difference was not significant.

Discussion

MAFLD is a clinical condition characterized by the presence of hepatic steatosis affecting at least 5% of hepatocytes in individuals who consume little to no alcohol (Younossi et al. 2021). This study employed HFD to induce MAFLD in the experimental animals, consisting of

Figure 3. Food and caloric intake profiles of each group. A food intake; B caloric intake. $**p \leq 0.01$; $***p \leq 0.001$ significant against normal chow group. Data are shown as mean \pm SEM (n = 8).

Figure 4. Macroscopic and histopathological analysis with HE staining of the liver. **A.** Normal chow; **B.** HFD; **C.** HFD + EGCG 25 mg/kg. Yellow arrows indicate steatosis, blue arrows indicate ballooning, and red arrows indicate inflammation.

Figure 5. NAFLD activity score. * $p \leq 0.05$; ** $p \leq 0.01$; *** $p \leq 0.001$ significant against normal chow group. ### $p \leq 0.001$ significant against the HFD group. Data are shown as mean \pm SEM ($n = 8$).

Figure 6. mRNA relative expression of LKB1 in the liver tissues of mice in each group analyzed using RT-qPCR. # $p \leq 0.05$ significant against the HFD group. Data are shown as mean \pm SEM ($n = 8$).

60% beef tallow provided *ad libitum* for 28 days. Typically, animal diets contain a fat content below 20% as an energy source; however, in experimental MAFLD models, the fat intake ranges from 45% to 75% (Carreres et al. 2021). Although HFD is often linked to obesity, in this study, HFD resembles a ketogenic diet, leading to weight loss among the experimental animals.

A ketogenic diet is characterized by a significantly reduced carbohydrate intake of less than 30 grams per day, accompanied by a normal protein intake of 1.2 to 1.5 grams per kilogram of ideal body weight or 1.0 to 1.2 grams per kilogram of total body mass (Basolo et al. 2022). The ketogenic diet has a high-fat composition, comprising 55 to 60% of total caloric intake, with protein making up 30 to 35%, while carbohydrates account for only about 5 to 10% (Masood et al. 2022). One of the mechanisms underlying weight loss associated with the ketogenic diet is related to the composition of the HFD used in this study. According to Rahmadi et al. (2021), the decrease in body weight observed in experimental animals subjected to HFD is attributed to two processes occurring in the body's adipose tissue: lipolysis and esterification. The fatty acids produced from partial lipolysis cannot be re-esterified at the same rate as lipolysis occurs. Consequently, FFAs accumulate in adipose tissue and diffuse into the bloodstream, leading to weight loss and an increase in circulating FFA (Rahmadi et al. 2021).

Based on research conducted by Donatello (2017), HFD reduces food intake by intervening in the regulatory system that detects increases in calorie consumption as a homeostatic response. It has also been reported that homeostatic processes primarily control the duration of food intake by measuring the calories consumed (Cavanaugh et al. 2015). One study explained that the ketogenic diet triggers appetite suppression. Dietary fat influences satiety and appetite through several mechanisms, including the release of appetite-regulating hormones and the inhibition of gastric emptying (Maljaars et al. 2009). Fatty acids (triacylglycerols) that enter the digestive tract trigger satiety signals. The ketogenic diet affects the release of satiety hormones, such as cholecystokinin (CCK), glucagon-like peptide-1 (GLP-1), and peptide YY. Under ketogenic conditions, there is a

Figure 7. mRNA relative expression of CD86 and CD163 in the liver tissues of mice in each group analyzed using RT-qPCR. Data are shown as mean \pm SEM.

Figure 8. EGCG mitigates liver steatosis in MAFLD by enhancing lipid metabolism through the adiponectin and SIRT1–LKB1–AMPK signaling pathways. EGCG facilitates an increase in adiponectin levels by inhibiting the phosphorylation of ERK1/2. This increase allows PPAR γ to bind to the PPRE located in the promoter region of target genes, thereby influencing adiponectin transcription. Once in the bloodstream, adiponectin is transported to the liver, activating the AdipoR2, which activates SIRT1. This activation leads to the phosphorylation of LKB1 and its subsequent translocation from the nucleus of hepatocytes to the cytoplasm. Consequently, phosphorylation of AMPK α occurs, which in turn influences the expression of key regulators of lipid metabolism genes, including SREBP1c, ChREBP, ACC, and FAS. EGCG = epigallocatechin-3-gallate; ERK1/2 = extracellular signal-regulated kinase 1/2; PPAR γ = peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor γ ; PPRE = peroxisome proliferator response element; AdipoR2 = adiponectin receptor 2; SIRT1 = sirtuin 1; LKB1 = liver kinase B1; AMPK = AMP-activated protein kinase; SREBP1c = sterol regulatory element-binding protein 1c; ChREBP = carbohydrate response element-binding protein; ACC = acetyl-CoA carboxylase; FAS = fatty acid synthase.

decrease in the secretion of the hunger hormone ghrelin, which is regulated in response to weight loss due to dietary changes (Roekenes and Martins 2021). The presence of fat in the duodenum stimulates the release of CCK and other gastrointestinal peptides that regulate satiety and food intake (Santamarina et al. 2015). This mechanism underlies the observed decrease in food intake in the HFD group.

EGCG, a prominent catechin in green tea, functions as a 67LR agonist, which subsequently activates LKB1 and leads to further phosphorylation and activation of AMPK (Fujimura et al. 2022). This mechanism is summarized in Fig. 8. A previous study demonstrated that EGCG at a dose of 25 mg/kg effectively reduced body and liver weights, lowered hepatic triglyceride and serum cholesterol levels, ameliorated

hepatic steatosis and inflammation, and improved liver enzyme profiles (Du et al. 2021). Although a higher dose of 50 mg/kg elicited more pronounced improvements in these parameters (Du et al. 2021), a study involving diversity outbred mice reported that daily administration of 50 mg/kg EGCG for three consecutive days induced severe hepatotoxicity in approximately 16% of the population (Church et al. 2015). Therefore, it can be concluded that doses greater than 25 mg/kg but less than 50 mg/kg should be considered for future research to evaluate the dose–response relationship of EGCG in MAFLD. This recommendation is based on the established efficacy of the lower dose and the potential risk of rare adverse reactions associated with the higher dose group.

Based on macroscopic observations, a normal liver typically appears dark red, slippery, and has a smooth surface texture. In contrast, the liver of the HFD group was paler than that of the normal chow group, which is attributed to fat accumulation within the liver. Hepatocytes that accumulate lipids, primarily TG and cholesterol, exhibit a yellowish appearance, characteristic of MAFLD (Podrini et al. 2013). Conversely, the HFD group that received a 25 mg/kg injection of EGCG demonstrated macroscopic improvement in liver appearance, as evidenced by changes in color and texture that resembled those of the normal feed group. The liver in this group appeared redder than that of the HFD group, indicating that the administration of EGCG enhances liver health in mice.

Apart from macroscopic observations, liver injury in mice was also assessed microscopically using histopathological sections stained with HE at a magnification of 200x. The histopathological changes observed, which include steatosis, lobular inflammation, and hepatocellular ballooning, indicate the progression of MAFLD severity (Takahashi 2014). Based on the NAS analysis, our study is classified as early-stage MAFLD, as the average NAS value in the HFD group is 4.6, which does not yet meet the criteria for MASH (Takahashi 2014). The data indicate that the MAFLD score in the HFD group significantly increased compared to the normal chow group and significantly decreased with EGCG therapy. Therefore, it can be inferred that EGCG therapy at a dose of 25 mg/kg for 14 days significantly reduces the severity of MAFLD in the livers of mice. This finding provides new insights into the potential for a shorter treatment duration of EGCG for early-stage MAFLD, as previous studies have typically employed longer treatment durations—ranging from 8 to 16 weeks—with models reflecting more advanced stages of diet-induced MAFLD (Gan et al. 2015; Khoo et al. 2020; Du et al. 2021).

Based on the data on LKB1 mRNA expression, the administration of EGCG increased LKB1 mRNA levels, potentially mitigating the severity of fatty liver in mice induced by HFD. EGCG binds to the 67LR receptor, inhibiting the phosphorylation of ERK1/2 (Santamarina et al. 2015) and enhancing the expression of PPAR γ and adiponectin (Santamarina et al. 2015). ERK1/2 negatively regulates the expression of PPAR γ , a transcription factor activated by ligands. Within the PPAR γ structure,

there exists a mitogen-activated protein kinase (MAPK) site. When ERK1/2 occupies this site, it triggers the phosphorylation of PPAR γ , leading to conformational changes that alter its affinity for ligands and cofactors, ultimately resulting in PPAR γ degradation via the ubiquitin–proteasome system and inhibiting PPAR γ expression (Kaplan et al. 2010). A functional PPAR-responsive element (PPRE) has been identified in the adiponectin promoters of both human and mouse genes. In adipocytes, PPAR γ and retinoid X receptor (RXR) form a heterodimer that directly binds to this element, enhancing the activity of the adiponectin promoter (Zheng et al. 2014). Indeed, as PPAR γ expression increases, adiponectin levels also rise (Dubuisson et al. 2011). Thus, PPAR γ plays a crucial regulatory role in gene expression, including that of adiponectin, which contributes to metabolic regulation and anti-inflammatory responses. Adiponectin in the bloodstream is subsequently transported to the liver, where it activates adiponectin receptor 2 (AdipoR2), activating SIRT1 (Santamarina et al. 2015).

According to the study by Bae et al. (2018), EGCG acts as an activator of SIRT1. It enhances both the enzymatic activity and protein levels of SIRT1, deacetylating the Lys48 residues on LKB1, thereby rendering it active (Santamarina et al. 2015). Once activated, LKB1 translocates from the nucleus of hepatocytes to the cytoplasm, which induces the phosphorylation of AMPK α . This finding is consistent with the results of Bae et al. (2018), where the administration of green tea extract led to an increase in AMPK phosphorylation. In the study by Santamarina et al. (2015), the administration of green tea extract rich in EGCG also resulted in elevated phosphorylation and protein levels of LKB1. However, based on the current research, it is estimated that the mechanism of EGCG within the SIRT1–LKB1–AMPK pathway not only influences the protein levels of LKB1 but also enhances the mRNA expression of LKB1. An increase in the mRNA expression of LKB1 leads to a higher production of LKB1 protein, resulting in further induction of AMPK phosphorylation and subsequent activation of AMPK. This activation of AMPK inhibits the expression of SREBP-1c and ChREBP, which are transcription factors that bind to the promoters of lipogenic genes such as ACC, FAS, and SCD1 (Santamarina et al. 2015).

ChREBP and SREBP-1c exist in the cytoplasm in an inactive phosphorylated state. Upon dephosphorylation, they translocate to the nucleus, where they stimulate the synthesis of lipogenic enzymes. Several studies have reported that activated AMPK maintains SREBP-1c and ChREBP in their phosphorylated forms within the cytoplasm, thereby preventing their translocation to the nucleus (Santamarina et al. 2015). Furthermore, activated AMPK directly reduces the activity of lipogenic genes, such as ACC and FAS, which are essential for de novo lipogenesis (Santamarina et al. 2015). This reduction in activity inhibits steatosis by suppressing de novo lipogenesis.

Fat accumulation in the liver prompts Kupffer cells to release chemokines that promote the infiltration of monocytes into the liver. These monocytes differentiate

into either a pro-inflammatory phenotype (M1 macrophages) or an anti-inflammatory phenotype (M2 macrophages) (Xu et al. 2021). In this research, the biological marker used to detect the presence of an inflammatory co-stimulator is CD86. CD86, also known as B7-2, is specific to the M1 phenotype of macrophages and is expressed on antigen-presenting cells, including macrophages. It provides the necessary inflammatory co-stimulatory signals for activating T-cells by binding to the CD28 receptor and the cytolytic T-cell-associated protein 4 (CTLA-4 or CD152) receptor, thereby facilitating T-cell activation (Matsui et al. 2017).

The research data showed that CD86 mRNA expression tended to increase in the HFD group; however, this increase was not statistically significant. This indicates that, despite the involvement of macrophages in the inflammatory process, polarization toward the M1 phenotype did not occur in the HFD group. Typically, the pro-inflammatory M1 macrophage biomarker increases during inflammation, as evidenced by elevated CD86 expression. M1 macrophages enhance hepatic stellate cell activation by induction of NF- κ B signaling, leading to the secretion of pro-inflammatory cytokines such as TNF α and IL-1 β (Pradere et al. 2013). It has been established that impaired macrophage autophagy can promote the polarization of macrophages toward a pro-inflammatory M1 phenotype (Liu et al. 2015). Research utilizing a similar HFD model has been unable to significantly impair the autophagy mechanism, as evidenced by the non-significant difference in microtubule-associated protein light chain-3 (LC3) expression, a well-known autophagy marker, between the HFD and normal groups (Rahmadi et al. 2023). Therefore, this may explain why no significant change in CD86 expression was observed between the HFD and normal groups. Conversely, in the treatment group that received an injection of 25 mg/kg EGCG, the expression of the mRNA marker CD86 decreased relative to the HFD group, although this change was also insignificant. This suggests that the administration of EGCG did not influence the polarization of M1 phenotype macrophages. Several biological mechanisms improve inflammatory conditions in MAFLD, including upregulating CD86 expression. Additionally, EGCG mitigates the pro-inflammatory phenotype by enhancing SIRT1 activation (Zhou et al. 2019), which is associated with increased adiponectin levels. This rise in SIRT1 activation inhibits the NF- κ B cascade in Kupffer cells, thereby suppressing the release of pro-inflammatory cytokines such as TNF- α and IL-6 (Niu et al. 2018).

On the other hand, the biological marker used to detect the presence of an anti-inflammatory phenotype is CD163. According to the research data, mRNA expression of CD163 in the HFD group tended to increase, although this increase was not statistically significant. This finding is supported by studies involving obese adults with MAFLD and MASH, which have shown elevated CD163 expression. In a study conducted by Nielsen et al. (2020), it was reported that CD163 levels are high in

liver disease and serve as a marker of Kupffer cell activation. Consequently, elevated CD163 expression indicates liver disease due to the release of CD163 from the surface of activated macrophages (Nielsen et al. 2020). The role of CD163 in macrophage polarization remains unclear, as several mechanisms underlying its regulatory processes exist. CD163 expression in monocytes and macrophages is regulated by glucocorticoids, IL-4, IL-6, IL-10, IFN- γ , and LPS (Etzerodt and Moestrup 2013). The regulators of CD163 expression are categorized into those that upregulate and those that downregulate it. Glucocorticoids, IL-6, and IL-10 are anti-inflammatory mediators that upregulate CD163, while IL-4, IFN- γ , and LPS are inflammatory mediators that downregulate CD163 (Etzerodt and Moestrup 2013). Hu et al. (2021) found that administering EGCG at a dose of 20 mg/kg resulted in the upregulation of IL-10 and arginase-1 (Arg-1) in the livers of mice. Therefore, further research is needed to explore the biomarkers involved in macrophage polarization in MAFLD mouse models.

The search for pharmacological agents to inhibit the progression of MAFLD, particularly in its early stages, remains relevant. Resmetirom, the first disease-specific treatment for MASH, has received FDA approval based on comprehensive data from 18 clinical studies demonstrating the drug's effectiveness in improving liver health (Mousa et al. 2025). This medication exerts its therapeutic effects by selectively activating the thyroid hormone receptor (THR)- β in hepatic tissue while sparing THR- α receptors that are associated with cardiovascular and bone-related side effects. Activation of THR- β enhances mitochondrial fatty acid oxidation, reduces lipogenesis, and promotes cholesterol efflux. By upregulating genes involved in lipid metabolism, resmetirom effectively decreases hepatic triglyceride accumulation (Knezović et al. 2025). However, while resmetirom shows promise in improving fibrosis and resolving MASH in patients with moderate to advanced fibrosis (F2–F3), there is a lack of sufficient data regarding its impact on early-stage fibrosis (F0–F1) and the long-term effects on disease progression (Fahim et al. 2023; Levien and Baker 2024). Consequently, resmetirom is not currently considered for the treatment of early-stage MAFLD. Such patients are generally managed through non-pharmacological approaches, such as lifestyle interventions and optimization of cardiometabolic conditions (Nouredin et al. 2024). A combined pharmacological and non-pharmacological treatment strategy represents the future in managing MAFLD progression (Gish et al. 2024).

Conclusion

Based on the results of the study examining the stand-alone effects of EGCG administration on LKB1 expression and M1/M2 macrophage polarization in the livers of mice induced by HFD, it was concluded that EGCG administration increases the LKB1 mRNA expression in the livers of early-stage MAFLD.

Acknowledgments

The authors would like to express their gratitude to the Department of Pharmacy Practice, Faculty of Pharmacy, Universitas Airlangga, and the Biomedical Pharmacy Research Group, Faculty of Pharmacy, Universitas Airlangga, for their invaluable support throughout the research process.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

Experiments on animals: 2.KEH.097.06.2023.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

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Use of AI

No use of AI was reported.

Funding

This research was funded by Universitas Airlangga through the International Research Collaboration Top #100 program of the Airlangga Research Fund 2023.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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